

Comparative transmission of three tungro isolates by green leafhopper (GLH)

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We studied the transmission of three tungro isolates obtained from the Philippines, Malaysia, and India by a Philippine GLH population. Adult GLHs fed for 3 d on plants of rice cultivar TN1 infected with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) of the isolates. The GLHs then fed for 1 d on nearly 2-wk-old seedlings of 12 rice cultivars using mass inoculation at about 4 insects/seedling.

In another experiment, we determined the reaction of these cultivars to RTBV using agroinoculation. Test plants were injected, 15-20 d after sowing, at the base of their stems with 50 µl of a viscous suspension of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* A₄ (pRTRB 1162) using a Hamilton microsyringe.

About 4.5 d after inoculation, we compared the test plants with the uninoculated control plants to determine reduction in plant height, leaf discoloration, and RTBV and RTSV infection, which was monitored by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. The relative concentrations of RTBV-DNA in agroinfected plants was determined by nucleic acid hybridization method using ³²P-labeled full-length cloned RTBV DNA (pJIIS2).

The transmission profiles of RTBV and RTSV either singly or together varied between the isolates. The Indian isolate produced higher proportions of doubly infected plants on cultivar TKM6 than did the other isolates. The Malaysian isolate produced more doubly infected plants on cultivars ASD7, Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan, Balimau Putih, and TKM6 than did the Philippine isolate. The Malaysian isolate also produced more severe yellow-orange leaf discoloration on cultivar ASD7 than did the Indian isolate, which was more severe than the Philippine isolate. Agroinfected RTBV plants of cultivars ASD7 and Ptb 18 produced the most severe yellow-orange discoloration.

Reaction of 12 rice cultivars to RTRV and relative concentration of RTRV-DNA in agroinoculated plants.

Cultivar	Reaction ^a to		Reaction to RTBV by agroinoculation ^d (% infection)	RTBV-DNA concentration in plants relative to that in TN1 ^e
	GLH ^b	Tungro ^c		
ASD7	R	I	S	High
Ptb 18	R	I	S	High
ARC 11554	R	R	S	Low
Gampoi 30-12-15	R	R	S	Intermediate
Pankhari 203	MR	R	S	Low
Utri Merah	S	R	I	Low
Utri Rajapan	S	R	S	Low
Blimau Putih	S	R	I	Low
Vikrmanarya ^f	-	R	S	-
FK135	S	S	S	-
TKM6	S	S	S	High
TN1	S	S	S	N/A

^a IRR1 data. ^b Based on seedling damage rating (IRRI). ^c Based on percentage infection in mass inoculation in cages. ^d I (intermediate) = 31-60%. S. (susceptible) = more than 61%. ^e Low = less than 20%. intermediate = 20-40%. high = more than 41%. -, = not determined, N/A = not available. ^f Dr. A. Gosh. Hyderabad. India, pers. comm.

Results showed that most of the cultivars that appeared resistant by leafhopper inoculation were apparently susceptible by agroinoculation (see table). Except for two GLH-susceptible cultivars, Utri Merah and Balimau Putih, plants infected with RTBV by agroinoculation fell into the susceptible category. The relative concentration of RTBV-DNA in Utri Merah, Balimau Putih, Utri Rajapan, ARC11554 was low, while that in TN1, ASD7, Ptb 18, and TKM6 was high.

Our results provide additional evidence that Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan, Balimau Putih, ARC 11554, and Gampoi 30-12-15 show some resistance to RTBV when inoculated by GLH. But on agroinoculation, only Utri Merah and Balimau Putih show any resistance. Thus, agroinoculation is a promising technique for determining true resistance in rice while avoiding the effect of leafhopper resistance. □

Dependence of incubation period and symptoms of rice tungro disease (RTD) on infection stage in ricefields

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For both field epidemiological studies and management of RTD, it is essential to estimate when and how many hills were infected. Diagnosis based on visible symptoms is often the most practical method to quickly survey fields. To improve visual diagnosis, we studied how incubation period and duration of RTD symptoms are affected by infection stage.

Experiments were laid out in a field at Celuk Field Laboratory, Bali, late 1989 in the dry season when RTD occurrence was negligible. Variety Krueng Aceh was transplanted 21 d after sowing. For inoculation in the field, one outer stem of

a hill was inserted in a glass tube, supported by an erect stick. A *Nephotettix virescens* adult was released in it for 1 d after 1 d of access to RTD-diseased hills. Inoculation 1 d before transplanting (DBT) was made in test tubes. We observed plants daily for 5 wk. We graded symptoms and confirmed diagnosis by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay test.

The incubation period was positively correlated with the infection stage except at 1 DBT (see table). The infection at 1 DBT showed inconspicuous, pale-yellow discoloration, and prolonged duration of incubation, Gr. 1, and Gr. 2. Plants infected at 1-5 wk after transplanting (WT) developed the typical leaf-yellowing symptoms. Duration of Gr. 3 for those infected at 1-3 WT lasted less than 2 wk. Stunted leaves remained the only visible symptom after the yellow ones dropped off.

As healthy plants covered infected ones in the same hill, it became difficult to detect infection unless symptom records were available. In contrast, leaf yellowing at 5 WT lasted until 10 WT when the

RTD symptom development in plants infected at different stages in the field. Bali, Indonesia, 1989 dry season.

Stage at inoculation	Plants tested (no.)	Plants infected (no.)	Mean duration ^d (d)				
			Incubation ^b	Gr. 1-Gr. 2	Gr. 2-Gr. 3	Gr. 3-Gr. 4	Gr. 4-Gr. 5
1 DBT	28	14	11.28 b	1.14 c	9.71 d	7.85 a	2.92 a
1 WT	27	13	8.92 a	0.00 a	3.30 bc	7.38 a	14.91 c
2 WT	27	16	9.18 a	0.25 ab	2.93 b	13.37 b	6.12 b
3 WT	27	8	11.12 b	0.37 b	1.50 a	13.37 b	6.87 b
5 WT	27	11	14.54 c	0.27 ab	4.72 c	-	-
7 WT	27	8	18.37 d	1.62 d	-	-	-

^a In a column means followed by the same letter are not significant different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b Incubation = from infection to Gr. 1.; Gr. 1, <50% of a leaf discolored; Gr. 2, >50% of a leaf discolored; Gr. 4, all discolored leaves dry but still attached; Gr. 5, leaves stunted but not yellow or dry.

observation was terminated. Plants infected at 7 WT did not develop Gr. 3 symptoms. Distinct changes in leaf color did not occur, but panicle development was affected in plants infected at 9 WT.

RTD-infected plants in fields develop symptoms different from those in the laboratory. Many of the hills infected at early stages are overlooked if leaf yellowing is the basis for diagnosis. We confirmed that this holds for many susceptible varieties, such as IR36 and IR64. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Damage by rice thrips and defoliators in southern Bhutan

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We sampled modern rice varieties (MVs) BR153, Jaya, and BW293-2 and traditional varieties (TVs) Atti, Dhursray, and Mashino bhog for rice thrip damage during Aug 1989 in 11 fields in Gaylephug, Bhutan. Crop age was 26-60 d after transplanting (DT). We recorded damaged leaves from three replications of 20 randomly selected hills per field.

Seven fields in four villages were sampled for damage by defoliators. Rice varieties were the same except for

Table 1. Damage to rice leaves due to feeding of *Haplothrips* sp. Gaylephug, Bhutan, August 1989.

Location	Variety	Crop age ^a (DT)	Damaged leaves ^b (% ± SE)
Lodrai	Modern	26	26.9 ± 0.3
Lodrai	Traditional	26	3.5 ± 0.1
Bhur Farm	Modern	33	13.2 ± 2.2
Bhur Farm	Modern	33	20.8 ± 1.3
Bhur Farm	Traditional	33	1.5 ± 0.5
Sumitar	Modern	35	9.0 ± 2.5
Panpani	Modern	45	10.8 ± 1.3
Bhur Farm	Modern	47	7.2 ± 0.3
Bhur Farm	Modern	47	7.2 ± 0.6
Bhur Farm	Traditional	47	1.8 ± 0.5
Surey	Traditional	60	4.7 ± 1.3

^a Days after transplanting. ^b Based on 20 randomly selected hills/field. Av of 3 replications.

$$\text{Damaged leaves (\%)} = \frac{\text{damaged leaves}}{\text{total leaves}} \times 100.$$

BW2Y3-2. Crop age was 45-60 DT.

Thrip damage was 7.2-26.9% in the MVs and 1.5-4.7% in the TVs (Table 1). Defoliator damage was 0.8-6.6% in the MVs and 0.4-5.8% in the TVs (Table 2).

The MV selections appear to be more susceptible to thrips than TVs in southern Bhutan. Defoliators, however, showed no distinct preference. □

Effect of foliar spray insecticides on brown planthopper (BPH) resurgence in rice

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Effect of foliar spray insecticides on BPH population. ^a Farmer's field, Banglana, Nakornpatom Provis. Central Thailand, 1990 wet season.

Insecticide ^b	Rate (g active ingredient/ha)	BPH population (no./8 m ²) ^a			Resurgence ratio (67 DAS)	Yield (t/ha)
		17 DAS	52 DAS	67 DAS		
		(BPH nymphs)				
		ns				
Alphacypermethrin + BPMC 41% EC	410	6.75	12.25 cd	770 c	0.142	4.5 ab
Alphacypermethrin + BPMC 41 % EC	820	8.75	8.25 d	487 c	0.089	4.6 a
Methyl parathion 50% EC	250	5.75	24 bc	8260 a	1.525	4.5 ab
BPMC 50% EC	300	7	13.5 cd	567 c	0.104	4.2 ab
Buprofezin + decamethrin 5.625% EC	56.25	8.75	13.5 cd	315 c	0.058	4.7 a
Cypermethrin 25% EC	25	6.5	40 a	2504 c	0.462	4.0 b
Monocrotophos 60% WSC	300	6.25	10 cd	415 c	0.076	4.8 a
Decamethrin 3% EC	7.5	10.5	37 ab	8104 a	1.496	4.0 b
Control		9	18 cd	5416 ab	-	4.4 ab

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^b EC = emulsifiable concentrate, WSC = water-soluble concentrate. ^c Average of four replications.

Table 2. Damage to rice leaves by defoliators^a in Gaylephug, Bhutan, August 1989.

Location	Variety	Crop age (DT)	Damaged leaves (% ± SE)
Bhur Farm	Modern	47	6.4 ± 0.84
Bhur Farm	Modern	47	6.6 ± 1.04
Bhur Farm	Traditional	47	5.8 ± 0.61
Panpani	Modern	45	0.8 ± 0.20
Patabari	Modern	60	5.4 ± 0.56
Patabari	Traditional	60	1.2 ± 0.60
Surey	Traditional	60	0.4 ± 0.10

^a Rice leaffolders *Morasmia* and *Cnaphalocrocis*, case worm *Nymphula*, and an unidentified larva

$$\text{Damaged leaves (\%)} = \frac{\text{damage leaves}}{\text{total leaves}} \times 100$$

We conducted a trial in a farmer's field in Banglana, Central Thailand, during 1990 wet season to determine the effects of foliar sprays on BPH. Plots of 12 × 15 m² were laid out in a randomized complete block design and direct seeded using susceptible variety Suphan 60. Nine insecticide treatments were applied at 20, 35, 45, and 60 d after sowing (DAS) using 500 liters water/ha with a motor-